

UDC 338.48(597) EDN: TTHAVG
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10435284

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ENCOURAGE LOCAL PEOPLE TO PARTICIPATE IN COMMUNITY-BASED TOURISM ACTIVITIES: A CASE OF THANH TOAN TILE-ROOFED BRIDGE IN THUA THIEN HUE PROVINCE, VIETNAM

Abstract. *The objective of this study is to evaluate the current status of local people's participation in community-based tourism (CBT) activities at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge in Thua Thien Hue, Vietnam. Research data were collected from 100 people, including 64 local people who have been participating in CBT activities in this area through a convenience sampling method. The study used descriptive statistics, frequency analysis, one-way ANOVA test, and Independent Samples T-test to answer the research questions. Research results show the difficulties of local people when participating in CBT activities such as tourism seasonality, low qualifications of local people, the division of benefits from community tourism activities, lack of capital, local people's dependence on tourism development projects, etc. Based on the research results, the study proposed some solutions to attract local people to participate in CBT activities at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge.*

Keywords: *Community-Based Tourism (CBT), CBT activities, local people, participation of local people, Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge, Thua Thien Hue province*

Citation: Nguyen, N. T. (2023). Encourage local people to participate in community-based tourism activities: A case of Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed bridge in Thua Thien Hue province, Vietnam. *Servis v Rossii i za rubezhom [Services in Russia and Abroad]*, 17(6), 56–67. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10435284.

Article History

Received 1 July 2023

Accepted 15 December 2023

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest
was reported by the author(s).

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ПОощРЕНИЕ МЕСТНЫХ ЖИТЕЛЕЙ К УЧАСТИЮ В ОБЩЕСТВЕННОЙ ТУРИСТИЧЕСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ: ПРИМЕР «МОСТА С ЧЕРЕПИЧНОЙ КРЫШЕЙ ТХАНЬ ТОАН» В ПРОВИНЦИИ ТХУА ТХИЕН ХЮЭ, ВЬЕТНАМ

Целью исследования является оценка текущего статуса участия местного населения в общественной туристической деятельности, основанной на достопримечательности – мосте Тхань Тоан с черепичной крышей в Тхуа Тхиен Хюэ, Вьетнам. Данные исследования были собраны у 100 человек, в том числе 64 местных жителей, которые участвовали в общественной туристической деятельности в этом районе, с помощью удобного метода выборки. В исследовании использовались описательная статистика, частотный анализ, односторонний тест ANOVA и T-тест независимых выборок. Результаты исследований показывают трудности местного населения при участии в общественной туристической деятельности, такие как сезонность туризма, низкая квалификация местного населения, разделение выгод от общественной туристической деятельности, нехватка капитала, зависимость местного населения от проектов развития туризма и т. д. На основе результатов исследования были предложены некоторые решения для привлечения местного населения к участию в общественной туристической деятельности на мосту с черепичной крышей Тхань Тоан.

Ключевые слова: *общественный туризм, вовлечение местных сообществ в туризм, местное население, Мост с черепичной крышей Тхань Тоан, провинция Тхуа Тхиен Хюэ*

Для цитирования: Нгуен Н.Ч. Поощрение местных жителей к участию в общественной туристической деятельности: пример «Моста с черепичной крышей Тхань Тоан» в провинции Тхуа Тхиен Хюэ, Вьетнам // Сервис в России и за рубежом. 2023. Т.17. №6. С. 56–67. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10435284.

Дата поступления в редакцию: 1 июля 2023 г.

Дата утверждения в печать: 15 декабря 2023 г.

1. Introduction

Tourism is a general economic sector, it has relationships with many fields and socio-economic sectors, including a close and inseparable relationship with the local community. Tourism brings many direct or indirect benefits to local communities such as creating jobs, increasing income, helping to build and repair better infrastructure and technical facilities, bringing understanding, cultural exchange, improving people's lives, and contributing to the economic development of the region and the country, etc. However, the connection and dependence of tourism on the natural environment as well as on the local community brings two aspects. It both brings great positive impacts and poses negative problems that threaten the ecological environment and indigenous culture. Therefore, developing "sustainable tourism" is becoming a need, goal, and trend of many countries around the world. In order to limit the negative impacts that tourism causes and ensure sustainable economic, environmental, and social development, a series of new types of tourism have been born that initially pay attention to environmental aspects, culture, and indigenous people's lives such as eco-tourism, discovery tourism, cultural tourism, community eco-tourism, etc. In particular, researching and developing forms of community tourism organizations is one of the most effective solutions to the problem of promoting tourism resources. And this form is being prioritized for development by developing countries around the world, including Vietnam.

In Thua Thien Hue province, Vietnam has made efforts to build many community based-tourism models in poor rural areas with tourism potential for many years. Some localities have strongly developed forms of organizing community tourism such as Phuoc Tich ancient village in Phong Dien district, Suoi Voi tourist area in Phu Loc district, Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge, Huyen Tran Cultural Center, An Tay Ward, Hue city. Among them, Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge is one of the leading destinations in exploiting and strongly developing local community-based tourism.

Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge located in Thanh Thuy Chanh village, Thuy Thanh commune, Huong Thuy town, Thua Thien Hue province is a national historical relic. Along with the extremely rich system of natural and human tourism resources, especially in the past many years, Thua Thien Hue Department of Tourism has coordinated with the Japanese International Cooperation Agency (JICA) to take place community tourism activities here. However, in the process of development, this form of organization still faces many limitations and difficulties affecting the participation of local people.

This study focused on analyzing the current situation of Thanh Thuy Chanh village people's participation in community-based tourism activities. On that basis, the article proposed solutions to promote the active participation of the local people in community tourism development at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge.

2. Literature review

Community-based tourism has been mentioned in development discourse around the world since the 70s of the twentieth century. It not only brings attractive economic benefits but also has many cultural and social significance. CBT began to become more known in Vietnam in the 90s of the twentieth century. This is a new type of tourism that has been strongly deployed and become popular in recent years [9] and it is a new approach that creates opportunities to promote Vietnam's image in the international market.

The concept of community-based tourism has appeared in many studies (Nelson, 2004; Ånstrand, M., 2006; Simpson, 2008; Okazaki, 2008; Honggang et al., 2009; Mtapuri & Giampiccoli, 2016). However, each researcher has different definitions depending on their approach and understanding.

Local communities play an important role in tourism development [8] and community participation in tourism contributes to protecting the environment and maintaining the cultural identity of local communities [1]. Local community participation plays a role in promoting sustainable tourism development [18]. Therefore, it is considered

one of the popular research topics for many researchers (see, for instance, Simmons, 1994; Dei, 2000; Tosun, 2006; Shani & Pizam, 2011; Dogra & Gupta, 2012; Su & Wall, 2014; Kala & Bagri, 2018; Thetsane, 2019, etc.). Many researchers have attempted to develop a series of general models of community participation. However, within the scope of this research, we used Tosun's (2006) model of forms of community participation.

Author Tosun's model proposed three forms of participation of people and communities in tourism development including spontaneous participation, induced participation, and coercive participation.

Table 1 – Forms of community participation

<i>Forms of participation</i>	<i>Definition of participation forms</i>
1 Spontaneous Participation	Bottom-up; active participation; direct participation; participate in decision making, authentic participation; self planning
2 Induced Participation	Top-down; passive; formal; mostly indirect; degree of tokenism, manipulation; pseudo-participation; participation in implementation and sharing benefits; choice between proposed alternatives and feedback
3 Coercive Participation	Top-down, passive; mostly indirect, formal; participation in implementation, but not necessarily sharing benefits; choice between proposed limited alternatives or no choice; paternalism, non-participation, high degree of tokenism and manipulation

According to Tosun's model, "spontaneous participation" is the giving of management and decision-making rights to the local community and proposes an ideal model of community participation in the field of tourism, It demonstrates the civil rights of the people and it will certainly receive enthusiastic support from the community.

For the type of "induced participation", the community can express their subjective opinions on the tourism development process. This type is only formal, the participation of the local community is passive, they only participate in solving

tourism development problems without having the right to make decisions.

In the form of "participation by coercion", local people are not allowed to participate in the decision-making process as in the form of "induced participation". All decisions are held by groups with higher power, and the distribution of benefits is almost non-existent for the people. This form will certainly not be supported by the community and it will be difficult to achieve sustainability in tourism development activities.

3. Research methods

This paper used qualitative research methods including research methods and document synthesis. We synthesized and analyzed scientific articles related to CBT and forms of participation of local communities in CBT activities. The expert interview method was also used in the article to determine the model, scale, and survey variables.

Besides, we also combined quantitative research methods and built a questionnaire. The sample was selected using the convenience sampling method. The sample size applied in the study was based on the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) requirements from the research of Hair & et al. [5]. The minimum sample size must be 5 times the total number of observed variables, or in other words, determined at a ratio of 5:1 [12]. In the theoretical research model, there were 14 parameters that needed to be estimated, so the minimum sample size was $14 \times 5 = 70$ samples. Thus, to achieve the minimum sample number according to the convenience sampling method, 110 questionnaires were distributed to ensure objectivity. The survey was conducted using a Google form. Questionnaire processing and analysis of the data obtained were performed using the statistical software SPSS.

In order to evaluate the level of agreement of local people towards the activities involved and reasons to participate in community-based tourism activities, the questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale where 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, and 5 = strongly agree.

This study also tested ANOVA and Independent Samples T-tests for the difference in the

degree of agreement of local people to the factors when participating in CBT activities at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge. The significance level P is determined as follows:

- $0.05 < \text{Sig.}(P\text{-value}) \leq 0.1$ (*): The difference has low statistical significance.
- $< \text{Sig.}(P\text{-value}) \leq 0.05$ (**): Average statistically significant difference.
- $\text{Sig.}(P\text{-value}) \leq 0.01$ (***) : The difference is highly statistically significant.
- $\text{Sig.}(P\text{-value}) > 0.1$ (NS): There are no differences in opinions between groups of people
- “-”: Compare Sig in the test table of Homogeneity of Variances ≤ 0.05 (Variance is not homogeneity), so Anova cannot be tested.

4. Results

4.1. Evaluation of local people's participation in CBT at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge

In order to assess the opinions of local people about their participation in CBT activities at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge, we surveyed 110 local people in Thanh Toan village, Thuy Thanh commune. There were 100 valid votes out of the total number of questionnaires surveyed by local people. Out of a total of 100 valid survey questionnaires, the number of local people participating in community tourism activities accounted for 64% and 36% of the respondents were not participating in CBT activities.

The survey results in Table 2 indicate that there were more females (59.4%) than males (40.6%) among the 64 local people who were surveyed. Of these, below 18 years of age (3.1%), between 18 – 25 years of age (14.3%), between 26 – 35 years of age (14.3%), and above 35 years of age (2.9%). Regarding the occupational structure, there was an uneven distribution among the respondents. The majority of local people participating in CBT activities are general laborers (70.3%). Other occupations such as students; businessmen, civil servants, and retired persons accounted for a relatively low, proportion of 12.5%, 7.8%, and 9.4%. In terms of the education level of people who are engaged in CBT activities,

primary school diploma accounted for 31.3%, secondary school diploma (28.1%), high school diploma (21.9%), bachelor's degree (12.5%), and respondents with other degrees accounted for 6.3%.

Table 2 – An overview of the survey respondents participating in CBT activities

		Number of participants (n)	Percentage (%)	
Gender	Male	26	40.6	
	Female	38	59.4	
Age	Below 18	2	3.1	
	18 – 30	11	17.2	
	31 – 50	29	45.3	
	Above 50	22	34.4	
Occupation	Student	8	12.5	
	Businessman, civil servants	5	7.8	
	General Laborer	45	70.3	
	Retired person	6	9.4	
Education level	School diploma	Primary	20	31.3
		Secondary	18	28.1
		High	14	21.9
	Bachelor's degree	8	12.5	
	Others	4	6.3	

Although CBT activities have been taking place at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge since 2000, through the survey results (Table 3), we saw that local residents have only participated in CBT activities in recent years.

Table 3 – Time and form of local people's participation in CBT activities

		Number of participants (n)	Percentage (%)
Participation time	Under 1 year	8	12.5
	1 - 5 years	28	43.8
	5 - 10 years	18	28.1
	Over 10 years	10	15.6
	Total	64	100.0
Participation form	Full-time	14	21.9
	Part-time	32	50.0
	Depending on the number of visitors	12	18.8
	Depending on the arrangement of the Management Board	6	9.4
	Total	64	100.0

The survey results showed that the majority of local people have participated in CBT activities for a period of 1 to 5 years (43.8%). This proved that the CBT model at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge has only grown strongly in recent years. Therefore, in order for CBT to develop more strongly, local authorities need to have policies to attract more local people to participate in CBT activities at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge. Regarding forms of participation, local people are participating in CBT activities mainly in part-time form with 50%. Because the community tourism activities mainly take place on the days of "The Rural Market" at Hue Festival.

Table 4 – Average monthly income and form of profit distribution from CBT activities

		Number of participants (n)	Percentage (%)
Gross income per month	Under 1 million VND	11	17.2
	1 – 2 million VND	38	59.4
	2– 3 million VND	10	15.6
	Over 3 million VND	5	7.8
	Total	64	100.0
The form of division	Received directly from the tourist destination	46	71.9
	From the local government / Tourism Management Board	16	25.0
	From the travel agency	10	15.6
	From friends, relatives	8	12.5
	Total	80/64	125.0

As illustrated in Table 4, the average monthly income that local people have received from CBT activities is mainly from 1-2 million VND (59.4%). This can be understood because most people have participated in community tourism activities in the form of part-time. Besides, the average income of over 3 million VND per month accounted for the lowest rate with 7.8%.

Regarding the distribution of profits from CBT activities at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge, it can be seen that mainly local people received money directly from tourists (71.9%). Because, local people primarily provided products to tourists by themselves such as souvenirs, handicrafts, food services, etc. In contrast, the lowest

proportion with 12.5% was the form of profit sharing from relatives and friends.

4.2. The level of agreement of local people on factors when participating in CBT activities at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge

To assess the level of agreement of the local people with the factors, the paper first tested the quality of the scale using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. This coefficient was used to ensure the reliability of the scale and observed variables. The requirement to be accepted is that Cronbach's Alpha coefficient must be greater than or equal to 0.6. (Hair et al., 2006). Variables that do not meet the requirements will be removed from the scale.

Table 5 – Test results of Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the scales

Factor	Cronbach's Alpha coefficient	N of Items
Participating activities	0.708	7
Reasons to participate in CBT activities	0.713	7

The results from Table 5 show that the coefficients of Cronbach's Alpha of all factors were greater than 0.6, so the scale ensures the permissible reliability.

From the survey data in the table above, we can see that the local people participated in a number of CBT activities relatively high such as: "Traditional art activities: Cham non, Bai Choi, Ho gia gao, etc." (4.09), "As a tour guide at the site" (3.84) and "providing food and beverage services" (3.67). In particular, traditional art activities have been the most attended by local people. Because Thanh Toan village is a countryside associated with agriculture, the people here always know how to preserve cultural identities and retain these long-standing traditional occupations. The criteria "Sale of goods at Cau Ngoi market" (3.39), "Provide accommodation services" (3.33), and "Sale of souvenirs products and handicrafts" (3.06) were rated neutral by the people. In contrast, "guide and manage CBT activities" (3.03) was the least engaged by the local people.

Table 6 – The level of people's agreement with participating activities

Criteria		Level of agreement					Average value
		1	2	3	4	5	
1. Sale of souvenir products, handicrafts	Quantity	0	10	44	6	4	3.06
	%	0.0	15.6	68.8	9.4	6.3	
2. Sale of goods at Cau Ngoi market	Quantity	0	15	13	32	4	3.39
	%	0.0	23.4	20.3	50.0	6.3	
3. Provide accommodation services (Homestay)	Quantity	0	14	25	15	10	3.33
	%	0.0	21.9	39.1	23.4	15.6	
4. Provide food and beverage services (restaurants)	Quantity	0	9	15	28	12	3.67
	%	0.0	14.1	23.4	43.8	18.8	
5. Traditional art activities (Cham non, Bai Choi, Ho gia gao, etc.)	Quantity	0	4	11	24	25	4.09
	%	0.0	6.3	17.2	37.5	39.1	
6. As a tour guide at the site, guiding tourists to experience activities: Cham non, boating, etc.	Quantity	0	5	15	29	15	3.84
	%	0.0	7.8	23.4	45.3	23.4	
7. Guide and manage CBT activities	Quantity	6	14	22	16	6	3.03
	%	9.4	21.9	34.4	25.0	9.4	

Table 7 – The level of people's agreement with the reasons for participation

Criteria		Level of agreement					Average value
		1	2	3	4	5	
1. Create more jobs for yourself and your family	Quantity	0	3	3	40	18	4.14
	%	0.0	4.7	4.7	62.5	28.1	
2. Increase income and improve family life	Quantity	0	1	19	22	22	4.02
	%	0.0	1.6	29.7	34.4	34.4	
3. Improve your foreign language and tourism knowledge	Quantity	2	15	13	23	11	3.41
	%	3.1	23.4	20.3	35.9	17.2	
4. Help yourself be more involved in the experience	Quantity	2	26	14	13	9	3.02
	%	3.1	40.6	21.9	20.3	14.1	
5. To receive support and incentives from local authorities	Quantity	2	12	16	22	12	3.47
	%	3.1	18.8	25.0	34.4	18.8	
6. Contribute to the preservation of local cultural values	Quantity	2	9	13	26	14	3.64
	%	3.1	14.1	20.3	40.6	21.9	
7. Create conditions to exchange and learn foreign cultures	Quantity	2	26	14	15	7	2.98
	%	3.1	40.6	21.9	23.4	10.9	

The survey results from Table 7 show that the criteria: "Help yourself be more involved in the experience" (3.02) and "Create conditions to exchange and learn from outside cultures" (2.98) were rated neutral by respondents. In which, the reason to exchange and learn from the outside culture was the lowest rated. Criteria: "Improve your foreign language and tourism knowledge" (3.41), "to receive support and incentives from local authorities" (3.47), "Contributing to the

preservation of local cultural values" (3.64), "Increase income and improve family life" (4.02) were relatively agreed by the local people. Besides, the reason "Create more jobs for yourself and your family" (4.14) was rated the highest by the respondents. Participation in CBT activities must have a link between the government and local people. Through that, the government needs to come up with policies to support people's participation.

4.3. ANOVA test and Independent Samples T-test the difference in the degree of agreement of local people to the factors when participating in CBT activities at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge

After performing the steps of descriptive statistical analysis, average value, Cronbach's Alpha reliability test, check the difference between variables using Independent Samples T-test and One-way ANOVA.

The Independent Samples T-Test is used to compare a quantitative variable's average between two different subject groups. At that time, we made the following statistical hypothesis: H_{F-0} : There is no difference in variance between the two groups of values. The F test is used to test this hypothesis. The test results are as follows:

- + Sig > 0.05: Accept the hypothesis H_{F-0} , meaning there is no statistically significant difference in variance between the two groups of values. We used the t-test results in the Equal variances assumed;

- + Sig < 0.05: Reject the hypothesis H_{F-0} , meaning there is a statistically significant difference in variance between the two groups of values. We used the t-test results in the Equal variances not assumed.

In case the qualitative variable has more than two groups, we will need to use another statistical technique, One-Way ANOVA. This test can be used to compare means between two groups of values like the Independent Samples T-Test. We made the following statistical hypothesis: H_{L-0} : There is no difference in variance between value groups. The Levene test was used to test this hypothesis. Inspection results:

- + Sig > 0.05: Accept hypothesis H_{L-0} , meaning there is no statistically significant difference in variance between value groups. We used the F-test results in the ANOVA table;
- + Sig < 0.05: Reject hypothesis H_{L-0} , meaning there is a statistically significant difference in variance between value groups. We used the results of the Welch test in the Robust Tests of Equality of Means table.

Table 8 – ANOVA test and Independent Samples T-test the difference in the level of agreement with local people's participation activities

Criteria	Sign	Independent variables			
		Gender	Age	Occupation	Education level
Sale of souvenir products, handicrafts	PA1	NS	NS	NS	NS
Sale of goods at Cau Ngoi market	PA2	NS	NS	NS	–
Provide food and beverage services (restaurants)	PA3	NS	***	**	NS
	PA4	*	NS	NS	–
Traditional art activities (Cham non, Bai Choi, Ho gia gao, etc.)	PA5	**	NS	NS	–
As a tour guide at the site, guiding tourists to experience activities: Cham non, boating, etc.	PA6	*	NS	NS	*
Guide and manage CBT activities	PA7	NS	NS	NS	NS

Regarding the independent variable gender, the study used the Independent Samples T-test. As for the three independent variables age, occupation, and education level, the paper used an ANOVA test.

For gender, the majority of participation criteria had a significance level of $sig > 0.1$, which means that the variance of each criterion between different gender groups was not statistically significant. Criteria PA1, PA2, PA3, and PA7

did not have differences among local people's opinions. This shows that whether people are male or female, their participation in CBT activities at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge was the same. Criteria PA4 and PA6 with a significance level of $0.05 < sig \leq 0.1$ demonstrated that the variance of these criteria between different gender groups has a low statistically significant difference. As for criterion PA5, there was a difference in gender, with average statistical significance

($0.01 < \text{sig} \leq 0.05$). Women are often more meticulous and skillful at work than men, so most of them participate in activities such as cham non, Bai choi, Ho gia gao, etc.

From Table 8, it can be seen that local people's opinions about participating in CBT activities according to age criteria did not differ. Criteria PA1, PA2, PA4, PA5, PA6, and PA7 did not have differences between the opinions of people with different ages. Thus, whether local people are old or young, their participation in the above activities was the same and the level of participation was quite high. Meanwhile, the criteria PA3 had a highly statistically significant difference ($\text{sig} \leq 0.1$).

Regarding occupation, local people's opinions about participating in CBT activities according to occupation criteria did not differ. Cri-

terion PA1, PA2, PA4, PA5, PA6, and PA7 did not have differences between the opinions of local people with different occupations. Thus, no matter what profession people work in, their participation in the above activities was the same. Meanwhile, PA3 had an average statistically significant difference ($0.01 < \text{sig} \leq 0.05$).

From the survey data in Table 8, three criteria with heterogeneous variance were PA2, PA4, and PA5. Therefore, evaluating these three criteria according to educational level was not meaningful. As for the criteria PA1, PA3, and PA7, there was no difference between people's opinions according to the criterion of educational level ($\text{sig} > 0.1$). Meantime, the criteria PA6 had a difference in educational level, with low statistical significance ($0.05 < \text{sig} \leq 0.1$).

Table 9 – ANOVA test and Independent Samples T-test the difference in the level of agreement for reasons to participate in CBT activities

Criteria	Sign	Independent variables			
		Gender	Age	Occupation	Education level
Create more jobs for yourself and your family	RP1	NS	*	NS	NS
Increase income and improve family life	RP2	NS	NS	NS	NS
Improve your foreign language and tourism knowledge	RP3	***	NS	NS	NS
Help yourself be more involved in the experience	RP4	**	–	–	*
To receive support and incentives from local authorities	RP5	NS	NS	**	NS
Contribute to the preservation of local cultural values	RP6	**	NS	NS	NS
Create conditions to exchange and learn foreign cultures	RP7	***	–	–	–

Regarding gender, the three criteria for reasons RP1, RP2 and RP5 had a significance level of $\text{sig} > 0.1$. Therefore, it can be concluded that there was no difference between people's opinions according to gender criteria. As for criteria RP4 and RP6, there was a difference in gender, with average statistical significance ($0.01 < \text{sig} \leq 0.05$). Most men do heavy work, so they often participate in community tourism activities to experience and relax after hard working days compared to women. Meanwhile, criteria RP3 and RP7 had highly statistically significant gender differences ($\text{sig} \leq 0.01$).

Local people's opinions on the reasons for participating in CBT activities according to age

were largely the same. The criteria RP2, RP3, RP5, and RP6 had a significance level of $\text{sig} > 0.1$, which means there was no difference between people's opinions based on age criteria. There were two criteria with heterogeneous variance, RP4 and RP7. Therefore, evaluating these two criteria based on age was meaningless. Meanwhile, the criteria RP1 had a low statistically significant difference according to age ($0.05 < \text{sig} \leq 0.1$).

Regarding occupations, local people's opinions on the reasons for participating in CBT activities were largely the same. The criteria RP1, RP2, RP3, and RP6 had a significance level of $\text{sig} > 0.1$, meaning that there was no difference between the opinions of local people according to the

Table 10 – Solutions to attract local people to participate in CBT activities at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge

№	Solutions
1. Key solutions for local communities	
1.1.	Solutions for local people's participation activities
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Local authorities need to discuss increasing the number of activities of the "The Rural Market" to more times, for example, once every 2 - 3 months, organizing a market session. – It is necessary to expand the space for organizing "Bai Choi" activities. – It is necessary to expand more "Ho gia gao" songs for the younger generation so that they can learn traditional local values. – Local authorities need to pay more attention to CBT activities at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge to attract participation from many other local people.
1.2.	Solutions on support mechanisms and policies from local authorities
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – In order to attract local people to participate in CBT activities, they need support from local authorities in terms of capital and technology. – For investors to develop community tourism, it is necessary to have preferential policies, reduce cumbersome procedures, and have incentive policies such as tax reduction in the initial period. At the same time, there must be a mechanism to use land reasonably for the purpose of organizing tourism business services. – Local authorities need to invest to restore traditional crafts and build craft village models so people can exchange and learn from each other. – There should be specific documents regulating profit division between local authorities and local people. The division must ensure reasonableness and must have reinvestment back into the community. – Need to attract investment from all levels and departments of the province and the State. – Local authorities need to introduce policies to encourage and reward outstanding individuals in creating products to serve customers in community tourism activities under the evaluation of tourists.
1.3.	Solutions for organization and management
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Currently, the locality has established a tourism management board, so it is necessary to clearly define for local people the specific function of this department, which is responsible for organizing the reception of tourists when they arrive in the locality: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Head of Management Board: Manage and implement proposed community tourism plans, and at the same time develop plans for local community tourism development in the coming time; responsible for managing individuals in the Community Tourism Management Board, service activity groups, and households participating in community tourism at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge, etc. + Deputy Head of Management: Support the Head of Management in surveying tourism activities; responsible for supervising work related to maintenance of technical facilities; ensure security and order work; plan training and capacity building for the community in tourism, improve skills for on-site tour guides, and manage the community's tourism fund. + Commissioner – accountant: Responsible for recording and managing books, monitoring income and expenditure related to community tourism activities.
1.4.	Solutions for training local people
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Training on skills to welcome tourists, local people need to be trained on how to speak in communication, attitudes and actions to welcome tourists, ensuring harmony, safety and friendly towards visitors. – Training on tourism business such as equipping local people with the ability to analyze supply and demand markets; build and improve products to meet tourist needs. Build product positioning in the market, determine appropriate pricing, enter into contracts or partnerships with travel companies and related partners, etc. – Training in foreign languages to improve foreign language skills for local people to create conditions for them to communicate with tourists, especially common languages like English. Training on how to serve special services of tourist accommodations. – Training on contents related to regulations on tourist accommodation activities, including general regulations such as fire prevention and other specific regulations for tourists.
2. Support and additional solutions	
2.1.	Solutions for staff training and establishment of local tourism departments and offices
2.2.	Solutions for developing infrastructure and technical materials
2.3.	Preserve national cultural identity
2.4.	Participate in protecting the environment and tourism resources at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge
2.5.	Solutions for market research, marketing, and promotion of local community tourism

occupational criteria. There were two criteria with heterogeneous variance: RP4 and RP7. Therefore, evaluating these two criteria according to professional criteria was meaningless. Meanwhile, the criteria RP5 had an average statistically significant difference in age. Although participating in CBT activities, all local people have received support from the government. However, farmers and unskilled workers with little capital have received more support from local authorities than businessmen and state civil servants.

From the survey data in Table 9, it can be seen that the criteria RP1, RP2, RP3, RP5, and RP6 had a significance level of $\text{sig} > 0.1$, meaning there was no difference between the opinions of local people according to educational level. The criteria RP7 had heterogeneous variance. Therefore, evaluating this criterion according to educational level criteria was meaningless. As for the criteria RP4, there was a low statistically significant difference in educational level ($0.05 < \text{sig} \leq 0.1$).

From the research results, we proposed a number of main solutions and supporting solutions to attract and encourage local people to participate in CBT activities at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge (Table 10).

These solutions act as an important tool to promote the participation of local people in CBT activities, so there needs to be close coordination between local people and the government. local authorities, Thua Thien Hue provincial tourism department and the state. local people, local authorities, Thua Thien Hue province tourism department and the government.

5. Discussion and conclusions

This study aims to evaluate the current status of participation in CBT activities of local people at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge. The findings indicated that the difficulties of local people's participation in CBT activities in this area were:

1) Tourism seasonality. Thuy Thanh is a commune located in a relatively low-lying delta, where rainstorms and floods often occur, greatly affecting the daily life and business of the people. Community tourism activities usually only take place during the dry season, from March to July every year. Therefore, the participation of local people was often unstable; 2) the tourism professional capacity of local people is still low, affecting their participation and development of tourism. Therefore, people's participation was extremely dependent on the organization and arrangement of the government and the Tourism Management Board; 3) local people have been too dependent on rural tourism development projects; 4) the division of benefits from community tourism activities does not have a clear regulation; 5) capital was also a factor that makes it difficult for local people to participate in CBT activities.

According to research results, to encourage local people to participate in community tourism activities at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge in Thuy Thanh commune, local authorities need to come up with practical solutions. This study proposed key solutions for local authorities including solutions for local people's participation activities; solutions on support mechanisms and policies from local authorities; solutions for organization and management; and solutions for training local people. In addition to the main solutions, there need to be additional solutions to attract the participation of local people, including the following 5 solutions: 1) Solutions for staff training and establishment of local tourism departments and offices; 2) solutions for developing infrastructure and technical materials; 3) preserve national cultural identity; 4) participate in protecting the environment and tourism resources at Thanh Toan Tile-Roofed Bridge and 5) solutions for market research, marketing, and promotion of local community tourism.

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